

ON THE NONLINEAR MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF SOME FIBRE COMPOSITES UNDER FATIGUE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Fatigue of materials leads to a change of their mechanical properties. Several glass fibre angle ply laminates were fatigue loaded and their stiffness and the material damping was determined over nearly four frequency decades and four load levels under strain control. The experimental results reveal the strong nonlinear stress-strain-behaviour of the specimens tested. This behaviour is described through a novel elasto-viscoplastic material model with two internal state variables. The model separates static and viscous damping and is able to quantify fatigue damage from measured stress-strain-data.

KEYWORDS: stiffness, damping, fatigue, nonlinear modelling, rheology, damorheology

1. INTRODUCTION

Long fibre composites are widely used in applications, where high stiffness and/or high strength at low masses are required, usually under varying loads. These non-constant loads lead to fatigue below the static strength of the material and to energy dissipation through material damping. Damping may be utilized to solve structural problems. Large damping may be desirable but can lead to component heat up and to destruction. Therefore no "safe side" exists in damping.

In both cases, fatigue and damping, the prediction of the material behaviour is of great importance for the selection of the material. As it will be shown in this paper, there is a correlation between fatigue damage and measurable material properties, i.e. the stiffness and the damping, or, in short, the stress-strain-behaviour. The concept of damorheology, proposed by OSIROFF, STINCHCOMBE AND REIFSNIDER [1] is followed. As an extension, the rheological measurements are conducted in situ and under the same loading conditions as the fatigue test. The measured experimental data from fatigue tests are described through a uniaxial elasto-viscoplastic material model. This model is capable of separating velocity-dependent viscous damping and velocity-independent static damping thus leading to nonlinear modelling.

2. EXPERIMENTS AND SPECIMENS

For this investigation, three different laminates were fatigue loaded and their mechanical behaviour was measured. All laminates are symmetric or almost symmetric angle ply laminates with fibre orientations of $\pm 30^\circ$, $\pm 45^\circ$ and $\pm 60^\circ$ for the glass fibre reinforced, cold curing epoxy resin specimens. The specimens were 4 mm thick, 15 mm wide and had straight edges. The loading was done by a servohydraulic uniaxial testing machine (Schenck PSA) under strain control. The machine was controlled by a personal computer which generated the loading signal, the strain, and measured the stress answer of the testing system and the actual strain.

The test programme is given in fig.1. It starts with a rheological cycle, followed by a Wöhler test. The rheological cycle includes cyclic tension tests with loading frequencies from $3 \cdot 10^{-3}$ Hz to 10^1 Hz in five steps and four strain amplitudes of 1/4, 2/4, 3/4 and 4/4 of the strain amplitude in the Wöhler test. In order to reach steady state and to minimize random errors by averaging, each step contains 10 individual load cycles. The rheological cycle contains 200 individual load cycles. For all test results given here, the maximum strain was 1% with a strain ratio of -1. The loading frequency during the Wöhler cycles was 10 Hz. The test temperature was kept constant at 22° C, the specimen surface temperature never exceeded 27° C.

In order to arrive at a steady state for the material, ten load cycles per frequency and strain step were sufficient, i. e., one rheological cycle contains 200 load cycles. The number of load cycles in the wöhler interval is doubled from wöhler interval to wöhler interval. The stress-strain-curves measured during the rheological cycles are described through the dynamic modulus

$$E_{dyn} = \frac{\sigma_{max} - \sigma_{min}}{\epsilon_{max} - \epsilon_{min}} \quad (1)$$

and the damping

$$\Lambda = \pi \tan \delta = \frac{W_{diss}}{W_{storage}} \quad (2)$$

with σ , ϵ stress and strain, δ the loss angle and W_{diss} and $W_{storage}$ the dissipated and stored specific energy, respectively.

Within one rheological cycle, the resulting E-N and Λ -N-curves are named the "rheological fingerprint" of a specimen. The line-up of all rheological fingerprints of a test contains informations on the fatigue behaviour of a specimen. In addition to conventional fatigue tests, the damping is also measured and stiffness and damping are measured at several frequencies and amplitudes. Fatigue test and the rheological material response test are unlinked, but conducted under the same conditions.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The angle ply laminates were fatigue loaded up to $1.27 \cdot 10^6$ cycles under strain control with $\epsilon_{min}=0$ and $\epsilon_{max}=1\%$. Rheological cycles were interdispersed at increasing load cycle intervals. Fig.2 to 5 display the rheological fingerprints of the specimens. Increasing load cycles lead to a decrease of the specimen stiffness. All experimental results have in common an increase of the stiffness and a decrease of the damping with increasing frequency. An increasing strain amplitude leads to a decrease of the stiffness and an increase of the damping. Frequency and amplitude influence on the measured mechanical behaviour change with the number of load cycles due to

fatigue of the material. These changes are therefore an indication for the fatigue stage of the material. The introduction of an additional magnitude, the damping, and the consideration of the time dependent nature of the properties of polymers leads to a new tool for the fatigue detection and quantification.

The $\pm 45^\circ$ -specimen exhibits an initially strong decline in stiffness (fig.2) accompanied by a moderate increase of the damping with increasing amplitude influence (fig.3). At approximately 75000 cycles the damping reaches a maximum, followed by a decreasing frequency and amplitude influence. After 1 mio cycles, the stiffness of the specimen arrives at about 60% of the initial stiffness.

It has to be noted here, that, contrary to experiments conducted under force control, fracture of the specimens occurred very rarely. A stiffness reduction under strain control leads to reduced loads. This, in our opinion, reflects the real situation in many fibre composites with load bearing fibres and strained off-axis laminates

The $\pm 60^\circ$ -specimen has an even more rapid decline in stiffness (fig.4). The frequency influence on the damping disappears, leaving only a small amplitude effect on the damping. The early stiffness reduction is accompanied by increasing opaqueness of the initially transparent specimen. Intralaminar, fibre parallel cracks lead to light scatter, and static velocity-independent frictional damping. The stress-strain-curves at high load cycles show nearly no reduction of the specimen stiffness in the compression region (closing cracks) and a strong stiffness reduction in the tension region (opening cracks).

Conclusion

The material response of off-axis, matrix dominated laminates to strain is nonlinear and time dependent stress. The fatigue behaviour of fibre composites -and most fatigue is matrix fatigue- can therefore not be treated with linear models.

4. NONLINEAR MODELLING

For the description and interpretation of the experimental results, a numerical model based on rheological models was developed. This model is capable of describing elastic, viscous and plastic behaviour of uniaxially strained materials. It is based on the Maxwell model, which describes linear viscoelastic behaviour [2] and the nonlinear Masing model [3], which describes plastic deformation. Both models exhibit material memory through internal state variables. The first is commonly used for polymers, the second is used for metal plasticity.

The simplest arrangement of rheological elements, that fulfils the requirements of viscoelastic and plastic behaviour is shown in fig.6. The total stress in the model is

$$\sigma(t) = \sigma_E(t) + \sigma_H(t) \quad (3)$$

with

$$\sigma_E = E_0 \epsilon(t) \quad (4)$$

and

$$\sigma_H = E_1 (\epsilon_2(t) - \epsilon_1(t)) \quad (5)$$

With the Bouc-Wen-approach [4,5] proposed by KOLSCH and OTTL [6] the first evolution equation for the hysteresis stress can be written:

$$\dot{\sigma}_H(t) = E_1(\dot{\epsilon} - \dot{\epsilon}_1) - \beta_E(\dot{\epsilon} - \dot{\epsilon}_1) |\sigma_H|^n - \alpha_E |\sigma_H|^n (\dot{\epsilon} - \dot{\epsilon}_1) \operatorname{sgn}(\dot{\epsilon} - \dot{\epsilon}_1) \sigma_H . \quad (6)$$

The second evolution equation is:

$$\sigma_H[t] = \eta \dot{\epsilon}_1[t] . \quad (7)$$

Equations 6 and 7 form a set of nonlinear differential equations. An analytical solution is not possible. For the modelling of the measured stress-strain-behaviour, the equations were solved in an interactive optimisation process on a personal computer. The optimisation of the parameters E_1 , α_E , β_E and η was done manually, the computer programme solved the equations and displayed the results graphically. This interactive solution procedure was more successful than a purely computer-based optimisation, since the strategies for the optimisation had to be changed during the process and the experimental data needed additional interpretation. The model presented before is not able to represent long-term creep and initial, constant plastic deformation. The relatively simple four-element-model is therefore extended with a Maxwell element and a Jenkin element. The parameters of the two additional elements are not determined explicitly. Their contribution to the stress-strain-behaviour of the model is viewed to be constant for each optimisation and replaced by an increase of the pure elasticity E_0 and a stress shift towards compressive stresses due to stress relaxation under strain control.

5. MODELLING RESULTS

The quality of the parameter identification is controlled by comparing measured and modelled curves. Only a few typical curves will be presented here to display the power of the model introduced in chapter 4.

Fig.7 shows a measured and a modelled stress-strain-curve during the first rheological cycle at $f=1\text{Hz}$. Both the mechanical system and the numerical system reached steady state. The specimen $\pm 45^\circ$ exhibits nearly viscoelastic behaviour with an almost perfect elliptic shape of the stress-strain-curve. The stress-strain-curves of the hysteresis branch of the model (fig.8) show small amounts of energy dissipated in the friction element and the major portion being dissipated in the viscous damper. The stress-strain-curves after $1,28 \cdot 10^6$ in the last rheological cycle are displayed in figs.9 and 10. Both curves in fig.9 show sharp edges due to frictional damping. The hysteresis loops of the nonconservative branch (fig.10) clearly demonstrates the action of the friction element. The hysteresis stress is limited by the slip stress of the friction element, which dissipates most of the total loss energy during the slipping. A smaller portion is dissipated in the viscous damper. The stress-strain-answers of the other specimens ($\pm 30^\circ$, $\pm 60^\circ$) during the fatigue loading are similar, only the quantities are different.

A measure for the contribution of static and viscous damping to the total damping is the specific energy dissipated in the friction element, W_{frict} and in the viscous element, W_{visc} . The dissipated energy equals the area enclosed by the hysteretic loop. The modelling was done only for a frequency of 1 Hz and the maximum strain, which was 1%, for the seventh cycle of ten under the same conditions. The first Wöhler cycle starts after 200 cycles in total. Some of the results of the modelling of the mechanical behaviour of the specimens $\pm 30^\circ$, $\pm 45^\circ$ and $\pm 60^\circ$ are displayed in the following figures. Fig.11 gives the amount of specific energy dissipated in the viscous damper and the friction element during one load cycle vs. the number of all load cycles, i.e. Wöhler and rheological, the quotient of $W_{\text{frict}}/W_{\text{visc}}$ is given in fig.12.

The viscous energy of the $\pm 30^\circ$ -specimen is almost constant with the number of load cycles. A clear tendency towards smaller specific energies can be seen for the $\pm 45^\circ$ - and the $\pm 60^\circ$ -specimen. A steep decline of the viscous energy in the $\pm 45^\circ$ -specimen up to 200 load cycles is followed by a moderate decline with a slope similar to that of the $\pm 60^\circ$ -specimen. The first initial decline of the viscously dissipated energy in the $\pm 60^\circ$ -specimen may have taken place during the first 186 load cycles, which are not displayed here.

The energy dissipated in the specimen $\pm 45^\circ$ through friction exhibits a steep increase during the first 2000 load cycles and remains constant for $N > 2000$. The friction energy of the $\pm 60^\circ$ -specimen decreases steadily with the number of load cycles. For the specimen $\pm 30^\circ$ no clear tendency can be seen.

The quotient $W_{\text{frict}}/W_{\text{visc}}$ gives information on the fatigue behaviour of the $\pm 30^\circ$ -specimen. In fig. 13 strong increase for the quotient can be seen between the measured last but one and the last rheological cycle, indicating an increasing portion of friction energy dissipated shortly before fatigue fracture. The $\pm 60^\circ$ -specimen has a steady increase of the energy quotient, the $\pm 45^\circ$ -specimen is between the two.

Conclusion

The elasto-viscoplastic model introduced here is able to describe the nonlinear fatigue behaviour of angle ply laminates. Dissipated energy can be quantitatively attributed to viscous, time-dependent damping and frictional, time-independent damping. The stage of fatigue damage can be defined by measuring stress-strain-relations, followed by suited modelling.

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Fig.1: Experimental programme for a fatigue test and rheological measurements to determine the mechanical properties of GFRP-specimens from $f=3 \cdot 10^3$ Hz to 10 Hz and 1/4, 2/4, 3/4 and 4/4 of the fatigue strain.

Fig.2: The dynamic modulus of elasticity of a $\pm 45^\circ$ -specimen measured from $f=3 \cdot 10^3$ Hz to 10 Hz and 1/4, 2/4, 3/4 and 4/4 of the fatigue strain vs. the number of load cycles.

Fig.3: The damping of a $\pm 45^\circ$ -specimen measured from $f=3 \cdot 10^3$ Hz to 10 Hz and 1/4, 2/4, 3/4 and 4/4 of the fatigue strain vs. the number of load cycles.

Fig.4: The dynamic modulus of elasticity of a $\pm 60^\circ$ -specimen measured from $f=3 \cdot 10^3$ Hz to 10 Hz and 1/4, 2/4, 3/4 and 4/4 of the fatigue strain vs. the number of load cycles.

Fig.5: The damping of a $\pm 60^\circ$ -specimen measured from $f=3 \cdot 10^3$ Hz to 10 Hz and 1/4, 2/4, 3/4 and 4/4 of the fatigue strain vs. the number of load cycles.

Fig.6: A simple rheologic model to describe elastoviscoplastic material behaviour.

Fig. 7: Measured and modelled stress-strain-curve during the first rheological cycle of a 45°-specimen at 1 Hz after 187 cycles

Fig. 8: Stress-strain-curve of the energy-dissipating branch of the elasto-viscoplastic model during the first rheological cycle at $f=1$ Hz

Fig.9: Measured and modelled stress-strain-curve during the last rheological cycle of a 45°-specimen at 1 Hz after 1.28 10⁶ cycles

Fig.10: Stress-strain-curve of the energy-dissipating branch of the elasto-viscoplastic model during the last rheological cycle at 1 Hz

Fig. 11: Specific energy of three angle ply specimen dissipated viscously and through friction vs. the number of load cycles.

Fig. 12: Quotient of energy dissipated through friction over energy dissipated viscously vs. number of load cycles.